

CONTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL EDUCATION QUALITY INDICATORS

TDPU Senior Lecturer named Nizami
Jumaniyazova Zlikha Reimovna

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the implementation of preschool education quality indicators. According to the authors, the practical use of indicators in preschool education not only increases the efficiency of knowledge, but also allows children to control their own knowledge.*

Key words: *indicator, method, technology, competition, discussion, tests, blitz games*

In our republic today, it is necessary to develop a unified state policy in the field of preschool education, to strengthen the material and technical base of this field, to provide qualified pedagogues and educators, to apply modern educational programs, methods and technologies to the educational process, to develop new educational and methodological literature in this field. All-round intellectual development of children by creating a generation is an important profession. Also, in Appendix 1 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", important tasks such as "...fundamentally improving the conditions for all-round intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children" are defined. In order to improve the implementation of this task, the issues of fundamentally improving the quality of preparing children for school in pre-school education and creating its scientific and methodological support were taken as a goal.

Decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4312 dated May 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 391 dated May 13, 2019 "On measures to further

improve the activities of preschool education organizations" ” decision and other regulatory legal acts related to this field is one of the main tasks.

The first stage of the educational system - the content of the pre-school education system fulfills the important social order of fulfilling the state requirements and the tasks of the "First Step" educational program. According to the program, children of preschool age are given the first concepts of concrete subjects from the age of 3-7 years. Ensuring that the quality of education is the same as in the brochure requires the pedagogue to act in accordance with a number of requirements. In order to objectively assess this process, we believe that it is appropriate to set the following requirements for the activity of a pedagogue. For example, the presence of working documents of the pedagogue - work plan, observation-analysis and diagnosis in accordance with the topics of the program. Preparation for daily games and training - a book showing the development and progress (order) of games and training organized during the day. Availability of demonstration and distribution materials - preparation of tools that ensure the effectiveness of planned games and training.

The creation of the necessary environment for children's activities in the group should be aimed at learning specific subjects, taking into account the interests, aspirations, individual and age characteristics of children. Wide use of modern technologies of education - factors that have a positive effect on the quality of education: Information Communication Technologies, use of various modern forms of children's activation: competition, discussion, tests, blitz games, etc. Knowing and implementing the state requirements and the program - the pedagogue must have a good grasp of the content of the program and state requirements for the age group of children he is working with. Participation in various competitions and examinations - should participate as much as possible in the competitions and examinations organized on the subject of the educational institution and outside. Pedagogical campaigning among parents, based on the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of the group's parents, help to improve their knowledge through various means. Taking into account the psychological aspects of children's

personality - taking into account the interest of children in specific subjects, it is necessary to implement an individual approach to them. Monitoring the children's knowledge and making a final assessment of the process by determining the results - according to the results of each half-year, the children's knowledge acquired in the previous classes is monitored and diagnosed, and the content of the future work with them is determined. Active participation in the pedagogical process in the team - the pedagogue should regularly participate in the pedagogical councils, seminar sessions and competitions organized in his team with his opinions and conclusions of work experience. Studying the monitoring of children's learning at the next stage of education - if the pedagogue is aware of how the children he taught learn later in the educational process in another age group or at school, he can analyze the mistakes he made in his work and the achievements he made.

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